

Expected Goals Modeling in Football: A Comparative Approach Using Classical and Machine Learning Methods

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Abstract

This paper explores the development of an Expected Goals (xG) model for football using an open-source dataset from top European leagues. I compare logistic regression with more advanced techniques, including linear discriminant analysis, bagging, random forest, and neural networks. The objective is to evaluate model accuracy, calibration, and interpretability while maintaining transparency and reproducibility. Results show that ensemble methods and neural networks outperform classical approaches, especially when spatial and contextual features are properly engineered.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the application of statistical and machine learning techniques to sports data has gained substantial traction. Among the most widely adopted metrics in football analytics is the Expected Goals (xG) model. This metric aims to quantify the probability that a given shot results in a goal based on contextual and spatial characteristics. Unlike raw shot counts or goals scored, xG provides a more nuanced view of attacking efficiency and finishing quality (Mead et al., 2023).

The first generation of xG models was based on simple rules or spatial binning, such as the Shot Position Average Model (SPAM) by Riley (Riley, 2012), which aggregated historical conversion rates by location. Michael Caley introduced early heuristic models in the 2010s, laying the groundwork for modern xG evaluation. Today, proprietary providers like Opta, StatsBomb, and Wyscout use advanced tracking data and machine learning models for xG estimation. However, these methods are not publicly documented, making academic validation and replication difficult (Caley, 2015).

In this paper, we develop a transparent, reproducible xG pipeline based on open-source event data. We compare classical statistical models with modern machine learning techniques and evaluate their predictive power, calibration, and interpretability. In doing so, we contribute to the literature on xG modeling and promote best practices for data-driven football analysis.

2. Data and Preprocessing

The data used in this analysis was sourced from a public Kaggle dataset¹, which covers over 320,000 shots taken in the top five European leagues (Premier League, La Liga, Serie A, Bundesliga, Ligue 1) from the 2014/15 to 2020/21 seasons. Each shot record includes:

- Temporal features: match minute

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/technika148/football-database?select=shots.csv>

- Spatial features: coordinates (X, Y), distance and angle to goal
- Categorical context: last action before the shot, game situation (open play, set piece, etc.)
- Metadata: shooter ID, assister ID, team, home/away indicator

We performed several preprocessing steps to clean and enrich the data:

- Removed shots with invalid or rare outcomes (e.g., own goals)
- Created engineered features: distance (Euclidean from center of goal), angle (goal opening angle), weak foot usage
- Converted categorical features via one-hot encoding (e.g., `lastAction`, `h_a`)
- Filtered rare categories in `lastAction` to reduce noise
- Split data into four analytical subsets:
 - `OpenPlay_Foot`
 - `SetPiece_Foot`
 - `OpenPlay_Head`
 - `SetPiece_Head`

The response variable was binarized: goal (1) vs. no goal (0). Summary statistics show that goals constitute roughly 10% of observations, leading to a class imbalance that needs to be addressed in modeling and evaluation.

The cleaned and enriched version of the dataset used in this project was published on Kaggle at the link above.²

3. Methodology

xG estimation was treated as a supervised binary classification problem. The objective was to predict the probability that a shot results in a goal, conditional on available features.

3.1 Models Considered

Five models was evaluated, selected to cover a range of complexity and interpretability:

- **Logistic Regression (GLM)** — linear baseline with logit link (Menard, 2002)
- **Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)** — generative model assuming Gaussian class-conditional distributions (James et al., 2023)
- **Bagging Classifier** — ensemble of logistic regressors over bootstrap samples (James et al., 2023)
- **Random Forest** — ensemble of decision trees with feature subsampling and grid-searched hyperparameters (Breiman, 2001)
- **Neural Network (MLP)** — Keras-based feedforward net with ReLU activations and dropout regularization (Bishop, 2006)

²<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/mat126/shots-dataset-for-footballsoccer>

3.2 Feature Set and Pipeline

All models shared a common preprocessing pipeline:

- Numerical features (minute, distance, angle) were standardized
- Categorical features (`lastAction`, `h_a`, `is_weakfoot`) were one-hot encoded
- Missing values in categorical variables were imputed with the mode

The neural network had two hidden layers (128 and 64 units), 30% dropout, and used the Adam optimizer with early stopping. All models were evaluated using a 70/30 train-test split (or 60/20/20 for NN), stratified to preserve class distribution.

3.3 Evaluation Metrics

Multiple performance metrics was used to assess model discrimination, calibration, and overall utility:

- Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC)
- Brier Score (mean squared prediction error)
- Precision, Recall, and F1-score
- Confusion matrices with custom probability thresholds
- Calibration curves (10-bin reliability plots)

Initial experiments with ROSE sampling (Menardi and Torelli, 2014) were conducted but ultimately excluded in final model fitting to preserve realistic class proportions.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Model Performance Overview

Each of the five models was trained on the four dataset subsets (`OpenPlay_Foot`, `SetPiece_Foot`, `OpenPlay_Head`, `SetPiece_Head`). The results are evaluated on the test set in terms of AUC, Brier score, F1-score, and calibration. Models were implemented using the Scikit-learn and Tensor-Flow/Keras libraries.

The logistic regression performed consistently across all subsets, with AUC values ranging from 0.70 to 0.75. Bagging and LDA slightly improved performance but remained constrained by linear assumptions. Random forest outperformed all classical methods with an average AUC around 0.79, and the neural network reached up to 0.82 on `OpenPlay_Foot`, where feature richness and volume were greatest.

4.2 Detailed Evaluation by Subset

OpenPlay_Foot: Neural networks achieved the best results (AUC = 0.82, Brier = 0.15), while logistic regression scored an AUC of 0.74. The model was sensitive to feature engineering, especially the angle variable.

SetPiece_Foot: Performance was lower across the board due to fewer examples and greater randomness. Random forest and neural networks still improved recall significantly compared to classical models.

OpenPlay_Head / SetPiece_Head: Logistic regression and LDA struggled due to data sparsity. Ensemble models were more robust, but miscalibration was more pronounced here.

4.3 Calibration and Decision Thresholds

Calibration curves (see Figure 1) indicate that logistic regression remained the best-calibrated, as expected. Random forest showed slight overconfidence in the upper xG range. Neural networks tended to overpredict in the top decile, which is consistent with prior findings in deep learning applied to imbalanced classification (Guo et al., 2017; Rajaraman et al., 2022).

To mitigate false negatives, the classification threshold was adjusted to 0.3 for every model, prioritizing recall. Confusion matrix analysis (Figure 2) demonstrated a marked reduction in false negatives, especially for OpenPlay shots.

Figure 1: Calibration Plot of the Neural Network Model for OpenPlay_Foot

4.4 Feature Importance and Insights

Feature importance from the random forest model revealed the angle, distance, and lastAction to be the most influential. SHAP values applied to the neural network confirmed the relevance of these features, though interpretation remains more complex.

In line with Hewitt and Karakuş (2023), future improvements may include embedding shooter IDs to capture individual finishing skill. This was not feasible in the current work due to high dimensionality and sparsity.

Figure 2: Confusion Matrix (Neural Network, Threshold = 0.3)

5. Discussion and Future Work

This study highlights a central trade-off in xG modeling: the balance between interpretability and predictive performance. Logistic regression offers simplicity and transparency, making it ideal for quick diagnostics and live broadcast use. However, its linear nature limits flexibility, especially with high-dimensional or nonlinear interactions.

Ensemble models such as bagging and random forest provide improvements, particularly in imbalanced data settings. Our findings align with Bandara et al. (2024), who also observed performance gains by modeling shot context.

The neural network achieved the best overall performance but suffered from mild overfitting and calibration issues. Advanced calibration methods (e.g., temperature scaling (Guo et al., 2017)) or hybrid models could help mitigate these.

One limitation of these models is the absence of player-specific information. Currently, all players are treated identically, meaning that a shot taken by Lionel Messi is evaluated in the same way as a shot taken by a goalkeeper under identical contextual conditions. This is clearly unrealistic, as individual skill plays a significant role in shot conversion. A promising future extension is the inclusion of shooter identity as an explanatory variable. While this was avoided in the present study due to computational complexity and data sparsity, techniques such as player embeddings, mixed-effects models, or hierarchical Bayesian frameworks could allow personalization of xG estimates (Hewitt and Karakuş, 2023; Davis and Robberechts, 2024).

Key future directions include:

- Integration of sequential features or event chains, capturing the buildup to a shot (Bandara et al., 2024).
- Inclusion of player-specific effects using embeddings or hierarchical models.
- Enhancing calibration through post-hoc techniques (Guo et al., 2017).
- Real-time model deployment trade-offs: balancing speed vs. complexity.

Figure 3: ROC Curve of the Neural Network Model for OpenPlay_Foot

6. Conclusion

I developed and compared multiple models for estimating Expected Goals in football, including logistic regression, LDA, bagging, random forest, and neural networks. Using a large and well-structured open dataset, it shows that machine learning methods — particularly random forest and neural networks — outperform traditional models in terms of discrimination, recall, and flexibility.

The study contributes a transparent and replicable modeling pipeline and reinforces the role of thoughtful feature engineering. While classical models are useful in constrained settings, modern machine learning techniques should be favored when predictive power and generalization are prioritized.

References

- Bandara, I., Shelyag, S., Rajasegarar, S., Dwyer, D., Kim, E.-j., and Angelova, M. (2024). Predicting goal probabilities with improved xg models using event sequences in association football. *PLOS ONE*, 19(10):e0312278.
- Bishop, C. M. (2006). *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. Springer.
- Breiman, L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45(1):5–32.
- Caley, M. (2015). Expected goals in soccer: The future of football analytics. Available at <https://cartilagefreecaptain.sbnation.com/2015/2/10/8017787/expected-goals-caley-metric-stats-football>.
- Davis, J. and Robberechts, P. (2024). Biases in expected goals models confound finishing ability. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.09940*.
- Guo, C., Pleiss, G., Sun, Y., and Weinberger, K. Q. (2017). On calibration of modern neural networks. pages 1321–1330.
- Hewitt, J. H. and Karakuş, O. (2023). A machine learning approach for player and position adjusted expected goals in football (soccer). *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.13052*.
- James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., and Tibshirani, R. (2023). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: with Applications in R and Python*. Springer Texts in Statistics. Springer, 2nd edition.
- Mead, J., Reep, C., and Liu, H. (2023). Expected goals and the value of shots in football: An improved approach with temporal context. *PLOS ONE*, 18(5):e0282295.
- Menard, S. (2002). Applied logistic regression analysis. *Sage University Papers Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences*, 106.
- Menardi, G. and Torelli, N. (2014). Training and assessing classification rules with imbalanced data. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 28(1):92–122.
- Rajaraman, S., Ganesan, P., and Antani, S. (2022). Deep learning model calibration for improving performance in class-imbalanced medical image classification tasks. *PLOS ONE*, 17(1):e0262838.
- Riley, P. (2012). The shot position average model (span). *The Power of Goals Blog*. Available at <https://thepowerofgoals.blogspot.com/2012/02/shot-position-average-model.html>.